

New Uzbek - my eyes

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Annotatsiya: this article studies the changes that occurred in the republic of uzbekistan and we are giving a description of the update .

Annotation : in this article we will be talking about some of the chages I the republic of uzbekistan and development.

Annotasiya: its obnovleniya I izmeneniya v a mi opisivaem state, the republic of uzbekistan v proixodyatshie.

Access

To fit today's rapidly changing times of uzbekistan on the basis of the so-called land also is opening Jannatmonand to embrace changes. Do not look where the update you will be witness , the people of this nation more prosperous living conditions of the country with the president commented in words, folks are carried out for the forgiveness of our own life and life dream . Thus we can come to be newly created as an example of the important transformations of our constitution. The head of state aytganlaridek , should serve for the value of all things human, the human value above all things. The new constitution also exactly these ideas are promoting. New has entered a new phase of economic development of uzbekistan . Today our state cooperation with many foreign countries . Only the head of uzbekistan islam karimov to the development of the country, but the entire central asia and the development of integrated economic intended to become the center to get out of it as the head of the leader who have appeared. 2016-year 6-September striking changes in the date of the life of the country, is a historical event that brings updates ,if you say it is not an exaggeration. Shavkat Mirziyoyev from the date of appointment of the head of state in the republic of huge reforms and radical changes are carried out. A new phase of the current period respectively uzbekistan "Third

renaissance" period is to prepare the foundation. All of these huge efforts and guidance of the aspirations of the results ,it can be said . Put these in the new building of uzbekistan and put a list of some of the steps we can pass .

Initially, the strategy and action was called for many years, the development of uzbekistan islam karimov tadrijiy plan - uzbekistan islam karimov will serve as the foundation for the construction of New. Taking the analogy from the developed countries of the world , the state would also be competitive for the modernization of the state, realizing that only come out from the necessary reforms, the new long-term strategy to develop a new policy for uzbekistan for the development of the country and stressed the need to. For this purpose headed by the head of state action strategy — a long-term strategy for sustainable development of society and the state has developed. On the basis of the strategy, in particular, more than 30 national strategy and program, code 5, 250, and the law, more than 200 decrees and decisions of the president 3, and the social-economic, political-legal, scientific-technical, judicial, humanitarian and other spheres with many more on the development of normative-legal acts have been adopted.

Our president put forward a New state — of the people. Reforms in the country the main purpose of human life, freedom, honor, dignity, and prosperity is to protect the legitimate needs and interests of our people in the way of living is to create the necessary conditions. Within this aim, the people with a direct , open and transparent dialogue and the president of the people for the reception of the reception to launch the organization and legal , economic , and cultural aimed at the protection of personal freedoms. With their help, appeal may be made of the coming issues of the environment of our own people. With the initiative of the head of state of the republic of uzbekistan adopted the national strategy on human rights in the years close when you embarked on. International human rights standards and ensure the rights and freedoms of citizens applying the national legislation of the creation of prosperity and decent living conditions for people in a huge serves as the main criteria of democratic reforms directed to.

“The only source and the creator of the law – the people that” this is our country to the protection of humanist principles apply in the case of significant changes in the judicial system which is the leader in human values observed. The law of creation proceeding from the needs and thoughts of the people and ensuring their execution directly in yondashilmoqda. To avail the highest interests of the people at the heart of all of this is not going to be put.

In addition, the new science of uzbekistan, culture , development, education, innovation, technology and trained personnel who can contribute to our country in areas that are also mature as professionals to achieve the best results. In solving the social problems of the population of women "on the trail" , "young notebook" , "the iron trail", also it should be noted that the introduction of the system as alhida.

As a logical continuation of the development action strategy of uzbekistan, new strategies are being developed. The main focus at the development strategy, on the one hand, the development of civil society laws, codes, programs directed to accept the concept. In which the rule of law, while on the second hand, to ensure the consistent implementation of the constitutional reforms and the national economy, the development of a strong social policy implementation, the development of spiritual authorities, as well as global issues in connection to uzbekistan, a wide range of important tasks in the field of security and foreign policy qamrovda will be covered . New strategic development priority in the next five years of development of uzbekistan in the direction of our country at 7 practical work intended to be carried out.

Glorious new strategic development of uzbekistan at the following clearly defined goals:

- free upgrades through the further development of human value to establish a democratic state and civil society;
- the principle of justice in the country and the rule of law and the most basic of the development of the conditions necessary to convert;
- ensure high growth rates and rapid development of national economy;
- fair maintaining social policy, human capital development;
- spiritual development of the sector and providing a new level to the withdrawal;
- human approach to the problem proceeding from national interests;
- enhancing the capacity of our country's security and defense, utilitarian open and active, the conduct of foreign policy.

New received the decree in uzbekistan and the main idea of the new creation and the law of “the man, his rights, freedoms, especially, the value of the most important values” has recognized the principle that. Come follow over the years, “state – society – man” principle “man – society – state” to the principle of o'zgartirilmoqda.

In 2016 “on state youth policy” of the law of the republic of uzbekistan was accepted to the social aspects of young people from the age daavlat related policy formation and their intellectual, creative and in the other direction to find the identities of the potential noted in particular that may serve to explain the conditions for, and the measures that must be done to make the law xizmlat be strengthened with a more important event . They give young people more effectively, more comfort within the framework of this policy in the union of youth work and youth and the way to solve issues the agency was established. Close look to the statistics of the year that we have this work as a result of the union of youth of uzbekistan was only since the establishment of the employment of young persons 841 147. 2021-78 in the first half of the year 140 young people into work is placed by the agency of youth work, young students subsidized 684 5 was allocated to social protection of students were given the contract to pay the sums 127 350 million in need of funds. However, as this work is progress and this number may have seemed simple, nice material and moral support to the children of the family will not be given unless noted . One more successful project as one of Five "initiative" project can bring. This project is to be launched with significant changes were observed , in particular, provided employment to our youth also significantly increased the contribution to the development of the society. The new edition to a radically new level of education in order to get out “on education” the law was adopted. The age of this law in order to ensure that the shape get the education from correspondence with continuous education, in addition to evening and was introduced in the form of distance education. Dual education has launched.

Summary

He does not reach practical things like this adog'i listed. The interests of the people at the heart of all of this, and its human value are being tarannum the idea of freedom. The conclusion that I have made, opportunities, find our own place in today's times , that we may gain knowledge in the way of success in any other field or sufficient conditions are given for us. Is that something we should do, while the rational use of them, to get knowledge , to master the secrets of the craft , to the times of prosperity of the country experiences the world as a specialist hamnafas is one of the leading in the way to promote it.

Used literature:

1. Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "together we will build our nation Great and noble manly kelajagimiznj"
2. "A free and prosperous, together we will build a democratic state" , Shavkat Mirziyoyev.
3. The Constitution Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan